

Paper 8

**REINVENTING STRATEGIES FOR EMERGING
SERVICE MARKETING**

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ABSTRACT

Service innovation is a new or significantly improved service concept that is taken into practice. It can be for example a new customer interaction channel, a distribution system or a technological concept or a combination of them. A service innovation always includes replicable elements that can be identified and systematically reproduced in other cases or capacity to achieve a closer match between the two environments. The replicable element can be the service outcome or the service process as such or a part of them. A service innovation benefits both the service producer and customers and it improves its developer's competitive edge. A service innovation is a service product or service process that is based on some technology or systematic method. In services however, the innovation does not necessarily relate to the novelty of the technology itself but the innovation often lies in the non-technological areas. Service innovations can for instance be new solutions in the customer interface, new distribution methods, novel application of technology in the service process, new forms of operation with the supply chain or new ways to organize and manage services.

Keywords : Service innovation, improved service, improved service, technological Innovation

Introduction:

Main reason for the growth of service sector is due to the .The changing lifestyle, changing word, changing economies, technological advances modernization, liberalization, privatization & globalization polices. Can be attributed to the changing life style, changing word, changing industrial economies, changing population & changing technology. There is drastic change in the industrial & business environment because of two vital components i.e. services a information technology. Open –market economy has integrated India with the world economy & currently the services sector of India accounts for over 40% its GDP(1).In India the service industries is highly employee oriented and heavily overstaffed & organization like bank insurance companies etc are dominated by procedures rather than services of customers.

Importance of service marketing

Most services marketing involves some good and there is explosive growth in service industry an account of increased complexity specially and competitive nature of business.

Service & Marketing environment –

Good-services continuum:

Today, no tangible goods are offered to a customer without same associated service.

No services are marketed without some physical good's associated with product.

Study of goods – Services = Continuum facilitates marketers to know and plan their market offering. Computer manufacturing firm sell hardware but major part of the profit come from maintenance contracts or software solutions (a services) e.g.: IBM's Focus is providing "Solution to the small Planet".

Brand – Service customers do not switch brand frequently as compared to while switching products. Services firms like hotels and airline aim to achieve zero defection by providing pro-active services(2). A brand name which is well know and associated with high satisfaction level adds value of the service product and makes customer less price sensitive(3). e.g. - Taj hotel, citi bank, LIC.Brand of service – Marketers goal should be creating a good brand image and the strategy to achieve the goal is to develop a theme in totality.

The following tact's may be used in implementing the strategy. Include tangible goods as part of the brand image. E.g.- LIC lamp between two hands, Welcome group - folded hands. Service Guarantee –Tool of value addition –For the firm to become a value added business firm it must develop a reputation of service guarantee. 1) Unconditional 2) Easy to understand and communication

3). Meaningful 4). Easy to invoke 5) quick and easy to collect.

Challenges in Services Marketing in India

Among the world's to 15 countries in terms of G.D.P., India ranked 10th in terms of overall G.D.P.and 12th in terms of G.D.P. in 2012. India has the second fastest growing services sector with CAGR at 9 per cent, just below China's 10.9 per cent during the last 11 year period from 2001 to 2012. Services share in world G.D.P. was 65.9 per cent but its share in employment was only 44 per cent in 2012. In India, the services sector had a high share.

in income at 56.9 per cent in 2012 with a lower share of 28.1 per cent in employment. In 2013- 14 the growth rate of the services sector at 6.8 per cent is marginally lower than in 2012-13.A service system is separates services from tangible goods on four unique characteristics– Intangibility, heterogeneity, inseparability of production and consumption, and Perish ability. A dynamic configuration of people, technology, organizations and shared Information that creates and delivers value between the provider and the customer through service. Existing literature Service marketers face vexing problems because of these unique characteristics. Service should be defined and studied as different from and a complement to products. Services marketing problems require services marketing solutions. Strategies developed from experience in goods marketing, are often insufficient

PRACTICES / STRATEGIES

It has been summarized the extent to which various business practices and strategies are used to overcome problems associated with service across all firms and different types of firms. These practices and strategies have been cited in the services marketing literature as particularly appropriate for service firms.

Pricing

Average responses across all firms show that cost –oriented pricing strategies are used more than competition/demand-oriented pricing strategies. Although services costs are difficult to control, yet service companies are apparently making estimates of costs to be sure that they are covered. Competition oriented pricing, although simple, may not provide assurance of covering costs(4). Demand-oriented pricing may be as difficult to implement as cost oriented pricing and does not guarantee that cost will be covered. Consistent with the relative popularity of cost – oriented pricing; local firms use the system significantly less than do state-wide- regional firms, probably because these firms tend to be smaller and less sophisticated. Local firms use the system significantly less than do state-wide- regional firms, probably because these firms tend to be smaller and less sophisticated.

Advertising

Direct mail and news paper appear to be more important advertising media than television. Television advertising is less appropriate for services because of intangibility. Unless service is associated with relevant tangibles (physical evidence at health/medical services; the equipment in a health club), service firm may have little to demonstrate. Service firms attempt to encourage word-of-mouth advertising find

Personal Selling

Over all, selecting personnel than firms which operate local, regional, statewide or national levels. This result may be due to the large number of people many international firms employ necessitating more sophisticated hiring practices.

Brand/Organizational/Institutional Image

Overall firms emphasize their marketing to project a specific company image. As expected, service firms which emphasize facility design most are those the consumer's visits: firms whose primary customer group is individual customers (travel industry), whose geographic scope is local (haircutting salons), whose benefits are immediate (child care centers), and whose need for the customers presence is high (health services) appear to be more marketing oriented than service firms serving end consumers.

Strategies to cope with fluctuating demand

Most prominent strategy for responding to low demand involved trying to increase business by calling on customer. Education of customers to use services during non-peak periods. Try to increase business by calling on customers. Letting employees work overtime, hiring extra full-time employees, and laying off employees. Finally strategies such as turning away business, taking care of regular customers and allowing others to wait, seeking sub-contract work during slow times, offering other services to use resources during slow periods(5).

National firms use the strategies to synchronize demand and supply, scoring higher than firms in other categories on seven of the strategies (taking care of regular customers and allowing others to wait, cross-training employees, offering price reductions, increasing advertising, turning away business, and calling on other customers). Size and Sophistication of national firm's most likely account for their higher usage of strategies to cope with the problem of fluctuating demands.

CHALLENGES

Formidable services marketing adversaries:- In many ways, most of business today are doing a lousy job of marketing. The cost of capturing customers continues to rise as buying processes become more complex and selling cycles lengthen. At the same time, customer s loyalty is eroding-on an average a U.S.based company loses half of its customers in five years. Forced by the changing expectations of customers and competitive posturing, most Companies expect that one –third of their sales over the next three to five years will come from new services and line extensions. Yet one –half of new offering launched fail to meet business goals. And two- thirds of new offering ideas never achieve market success. So currently above 50 to 65 cents out of every marketing dollar Invested in new offerings is wasted. The above marketing challenges are formidable enough and apply generically to any and all organizations no matter what they develop, sell and deliver(6). However services marketers face some additional challenges that Further confound the problem. Services are intangible:- Services are something that can be bought and sold but can't be dropped on your foot. The challenge of dealing with the added complexity of intangibility alone raises the bar. **Services are performed:-** Services are delivered live, in real time, usually at the customer's location. In many instances, products are involved, but it is the service provider who is on stage. The customer's perceptions are based upon the actual actions of the services provider. **Goals:** The goal of performing services is unique to each customer and more complicated. Although the process of delivering the service, such as on-site equipment repair or Systems integration, may be the same, the successful service provider makes the experience unique to the specific customer. The actual process of performing the service may stay the same, but variation is required to meet the uniqueness of the customer and the situation. The Services offering are personalized.

Customer involvement: With services, the customer often is involved in the service performance. In many cases, the service is performed up close and personal. Because of this, the customer often is involved in the actual performance. Each customer interprets things differently. Since the performer is right there, on stage, he is often subject to special requests that may not be a part of the original agreement.

Quality control: In services, quality control is conducted by the customer. The customer keeps the specifications in his or her head. The customer compares the service experience to the expectations developed prior to the performance. In fact, customer expectations often change during the performance, adding to the complexity of the performance(7). When the

services are improperly performed, apologies and reparation is the only means of recourse. A poor performance is usually discovered immediately.

Morale and skills: The morale and skill of service performance is critical. They perform during moments of truth in real time at the customer's location. They must be willing and able to bend the rules where appropriate, are creative in varying customer situations and the Accountable for profitability.

Service innovation:

Service innovation is a new or significantly improved service concept that is taken into practice. It can be for example a new customer interaction channel, a distribution system or a technological concept or a combination of them. A service innovation always includes replicable elements that can be identified and systematically reproduced in other cases or capacity to achieve a closer match between the two environments. The replicable element can be the service outcome or the service process as such or a part of them. A service innovation benefits both the service producer and customers and it improves its developer's competitive edge. A service innovation is a service product or service process that is based on some technology or systematic method. In services however, the innovation does not necessarily relate to the novelty of the technology itself but the innovation often lies in the non-technological areas. Service innovations can for instance be new solutions in the customer interface, new distribution methods, novel application of technology in the service process, new forms of operation with the supply chain or new ways to organize and manage services." A new or considerably changed service concept, client interaction channel, service delivery system or technological concept that individually, but most likely in combination, leads to one or more (re)new(ed) service functions that are new to the firm and do change the service/good offered on the market and do require structurally new technological, human or organizational capabilities of the service organization." This definition covers the notions of technological and non-technological innovation(8). Non-technological innovations in services mainly arise from investment in intangible inputs.

Areas of innovation – den Hertog's model

Husden Hertog (2000) who identifies four "dimensions" of service innovation, takes quite a different direction to much standard innovation theorizing.

1. **The Service Concept** refers to a service concept that is new to its particular market – a new service in effect, or in Edvardsson's (1996, 1997) terminology, a "new value proposition". Many service innovations involve fairly intangible characteristics of the service, and others involve new ways of organizing solutions to problems (be these new or familiar ones). Examples might include new types of bank account or information service. In some service sectors, such as retail, there is much talk about "formats", such as the organization of shops in different ways (more or less specialized, more or less focused on quality or cost-saving, etc.).
2. **The Client Interface** refers to innovation in the interface between the service provider and its customers. Clients are often highly involved in service production, and

changes in the way in which they play their roles and are related to suppliers can be major innovations for many services. Examples might include a greater amount of self-service for clients visiting service organizations. There is a French literature on service innovation that focuses especially on this type of innovation, identifying it as innovation in “service function”.

3. **The Service Delivery System** also often relates to the linkage between the service provider and its client, since delivery does involve an interaction across this interface. However, there are also internal organizational arrangements that relate to the ways in which service workers perform their job so as to deliver the critical services. Much innovation concerns the electronic delivery of services, but we can also think of, for instance, transport and packaging innovations (e.g. pizza delivery). An emerging concept of SDP is the idea of taking a "factory" approach to Service Innovation. A "service factory" approach is a standardized and industrialized environment for more effective service innovation, development and operations for the IP era.

4. **Technological Options** resemble most familiar process innovation in manufacturing sectors. New information technology is especially important to services, since it allows for greater efficiency and effectiveness in the information-processing elements that are, as we have seen, prevalent to a great extent in services sectors. We also often see physical products accompanying services, such as customer loyalty cards and “smart” RFID cards for transactions, and a wide range of devices for communication services.

In practice, the majority of service innovations will almost certainly involve various combinations of these four dimensions. For instance:

- A new IT system (technology dimension) may be used to enable customer self-service (interface dimension) as in the case of a bank contacting its customers.
- The ability to track one’s order or the location of an item that one has posted or is expecting to receive.
- Services may be delivered electronically, as in the case of much online banking and cash withdrawals from ATMs.
- A new service allowing a client to examine various options and calculate what they would be paying with different types of accounts.
- A new service will often require a new service delivery system, and changes at the client interface.

Features of services associated with service production

1. Technology and Plant (Low levels of capital equipment; heavy investment in buildings Reduce costs of buildings by use of teleservices, toll-free phone numbers, etc.)

2. Labor (Some services highly professional, esp. requiring interpersonal skills); others relatively unskilled, often involving casual or part-time labor. Specialist knowledge may be important, but rarely technological skills (other than Information Technology) Reduce reliance on expensive and scarce skills by use of expert systems and related innovations; Relocation of key operations to areas of low labor costs (using telecommunications to maintain coordination).

3. Organization of Labor Process (Workforce often engaged in craft-like production with limited management control of details of work. Use IT to monitor workforce (e.g. tachometers and mobile communications for transport staff; Aim for 'flatter' organizational structures, with data from field and front-office workers directly entering databases and thence Management Information Systems.)

4. Features of Production (Production is often non-continuous and economies of scale are limited Standardize production (e.g. 'fast-food' chains), reorganize in more assembly-line-like feature with more standard components and higher division of labor.)

5. Organization of Industry (Some services state-run public services; Others often small-scale with high preponderance of family firms and self-employed Externalization and privatization of public services; combination of small firms using network technologies; IT-based service management systems.)

1. Features of services associated with service product

1. Nature of Product (Immaterial, often information-intensive; Hard to store or transport; Process and product hard to distinguish. >>> Add material components (e.g. client cards, membership cards). Use telemetric for ordering, reservation, and if possible – delivery. Maintain elements of familiar 'user-interfaces'.)

2. Features of Product (Often customized to consumer requirements.>>> Use of Electronic Data Interchange or Internet for remote input of client details; use software to record client requirements and match to service product.

2. Features of services associated with services consumption

1. Delivery of Product (Production and consumption coterminous in time and space; often client or supplier has to move to meet the other party. Telemetric; Automated Teller Machines and equivalent information services.)

2. Role of Consumer (Services are *consumer-intensive*, requiring inputs from consumer into design/production process. Consumer use of standardized *menus and new modes of delivering orders*.)

3. Organization of Consumption (Often hard to separate production from consumption; Self-service in formal and informal economies commonplace. Increased use of self-service, utilizing existing consumer (or intermediate producer) technology – e.g. telephones, PCs – and user-friendly software interfaces.)

3. Features of services associated with services markets

1. Organization of Markets (Some services delivered via public sector bureaucratic provision; some costs are invisibly bundled with goods (e.g. retail sector). Introduction of *quasi-markets* and/or privatization of services; New modes of charging (*pay per society*), new reservation systems; more volatility in pricing using features of EPOS and related systems.)

2. Regulation (Professional regulation common in some services. Use of databases by regulatory institutions and service providers to supply and examine performance indicators and diagnostic evidence.)

3. Marketing (Difficult to demonstrate products in advance. Guarantees; demonstration packages (e.g. *demo* software, shareware, trial periods of use).)

Additionally, a number of more general tendencies in the innovation process in services have been noted. These include:

1. The industrialization of services, involving efforts to standardize services, to yield service products of predictable characteristics and quality, with economies of scale and improved delivery times. This typically involves the introduction of high levels of division of labour, with the use of pre-packaged and automated elements (such as pre-prepared meals, word processed templates for form letters, and the like). Standardization of the service products has become a competitive strategy for many firms.

2. Organizational innovation. Survey data suggest that services place particular emphasis on organizational change. Many important innovations in services involve combinations of specific new technologies together with organization change. The role of organizational innovations in services is very apparent – developments such as supermarkets and other self-service facilities are extremely significant in the development of modern service industries. Such organizational innovations will often have a technological dimension, whether this be very basic (e.g. shopping trolleys), or relatively high-tech (EPOS – electronic point of sale – equipment or ATMs linked into networks).

3. An important trajectory of organizational change has been towards self-servicing, without necessarily following this development all the way toward the vision of the client sitting at home interacting with the service provider via a remote terminal. Instead, reorganization of the facilities of the service provider permits customer self-service in the service establishment, saving on labor costs and often increasing user satisfaction as it is possible to make decisions anonymously and at one's own pace.

4. Beyond self-servicing, the involvement of clients as co producers is particularly important for knowledge-intensive business services, with the emphasis being laid upon clients' role in advancing the expertise of service suppliers, and identifying new avenues for its application. Web2.0 has brought “*user innovation*” to the fore in electronic services.

Service innovation and Public policy

In recent years policy makers have begun to consider the potential for promoting services innovation as part of their economic development strategies. Such consideration has, in part, been driven by the growing contribution that services activities make to national and regional economies. It also reflects the emerging recognition that traditional policy measures such as R&D grants and technology transfer supports have been developed from a manufacturing perspective of the innovation process.

The European Commission and the OECD has been particularly active in seeking to generate reflection on services innovation and its policy implications. The European Commission has also launched a number of Knowledge Intensive Services Platforms designed to act as

laboratories for new public policies for services innovation. Finland has been active in thinking about the policy implications of services innovation. This has seen TEKES – the

Finnish Funding Agency for Technology and Innovation – launch the *SERVE* initiative, designed to support ‘Finnish companies and research organisations in the development of innovative service concepts that can be reproduced or replicated and where some technology or systematic method is applied. Germany has also undertaken initiatives for services R&D, Ireland has been considering a services-focused innovation policy(90),

Conclusion:

It is inevitable that globalization has become the norm in the service industry. This is evidenced by a growing number of businesses that a service firm operates in more than one country. Those have since evolved their business practices. The changes in the world economy and business practices have driven the focus on service: the fact that services dominate the modern economies of the world; the focus on services as competitive business imperative; specific needs of the deregulated and professional service industries; the role of new service concepts growing from technological advances; and the realization that the unique characteristics of services result in unique challenges and opportunities. A service provider has to adapt to ever changing world economy, identify challenges, distinguish among pure services, value-added services, customer services, derived services and appropriately address these service sectors. By using major consideration for service innovation .The five principles of service design thinking: like User-centered: Services should be experienced and designed through the customer’s eyes. Co creative: All stakeholders should be included in the service design process sequencing: A service should be visualized as a sequence of interrelated actions Evidencing: Intangible services should be visualized in terms of physical artifacts Holistic: The entre environment of a service should be considered. and involving various types of Major or radical innovations Start-up businesses ,New services for the currently served market, Service line extensions, Service improvements, Style change

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